

Determination of the random spatial variation of the bending stiffness in composite materials

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Abstract. The macroscopic stiffness of a composite material is closely related to its microstructural configuration and multiscale simulation methods can establish this link through homogenization. In numerical homogenization, equivalent stiffness is usually described through stiffness tensor components, which are computed by applying specific boundary conditions (BCs) corresponding to characteristic deformation states, such as tension and shear. In this work, bending BCs are applied to compute the equivalent flexural stiffness in ABD matrix form according to classical laminate theory. In the case of random composites, the spatial variation of the volume fraction is known to significantly affect the apparent mechanical properties, which can be described by random fields. The case of a random short fiber-reinforced composite is investigated herein, and random fields of the equivalent stiffness are computed. Essentially, random fields of the ABD matrix are determined, whose components correspond to bending as well as extension/shear BCs, and their statistics are compared. The computed random stiffness components can be used in stochastic finite element analysis of composite shell structures.

Keywords: Composite materials, Homogenization, Bending stiffness, Random fields

1 Introduction

Multiscale methods rely on homogenization approaches to explain the macroscopic behavior of heterogeneous materials from their microstructure. In 2D or 3D structures, this typically involves application of macroscopic extension and shear BCs on a volume element, which leads to the effective stiffness [7]. In the case of composite shells, alternative methods are required for the computation of an effective bending stiffness. Relying on classical laminate theory (CLT) [1], there have been numerous homogenization techniques proposed for composite shells [5],[6],[10],[4]. These involve computation of the effective ABD stiffness matrix, which relates forces to strains and moments to curvatures, via application of extension/shear and bending/torsion BCs, respectively.

However, the case of the effective properties of random composite shells has not been sufficiently investigated in literature. In [11], stochastic homogenization analysis of laminates consisting of fiber reinforced composites is performed, considering random Young's moduli for the constituent materials and random fiber orientation. In [13], the case of random spatially varying ply orientations is investigated, and the resulting variability in the properties of the laminate, described using lamination parameters, is quantified. Lastly, in [3], a variationally consistent homogenization framework for Reissner-Mindlin plate elements is proposed, which is also applied to stochastic volume elements (SVEs) and the statistics of effective bending properties are examined.

In this work, the random spatial variation of the effective bending stiffness is investigated considering random fields [2],[12] of the ABD matrix components. An ABD matrix homogenization method is first proposed, and tested on a random unidirectional (UD) composite. Subsequently, random fields of the ABD matrix components are computed based on CT images of a real short fiber composite. Useful conclusions are derived regarding spatial variability and cross-correlation, while the results can be further employed for conducting a stochastic response analysis in future works.

2 Methodology

2.1 Classical Laminate Theory

In CLT, a composite laminate consists of several layers or laminae with different properties or alignment [1]. Each lamina is considered an orthotropic material, therefore its inplane behavior can be described by the following equation:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{xx} \\ \sigma_{yy} \\ \tau_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & 0 \\ C_{21} & C_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & C_{33} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{xx} \\ \varepsilon_{yy} \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{or} \quad \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{C} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{C} is the elasticity matrix.

For the computation of the mechanical properties of laminates according to CLT, a number of assumptions are made. Each lamina is a homogeneous material and there is perfect bonding between each layer. Inplane stiffness is determined by assuming plane stress conditions. With regard to bending behavior, the assumptions of the Kirchoff-Love theory hold, which means that normals to the midplane remain normal and straight, while their lengths do not change. It should be noted that, as the thickness of the laminate increases, the Kirchoff-Love assumptions can lead to inaccurate stiffness estimates.

Under the above assumptions, the relationship between force/moment resultants and mid-surface strains/curvatures according to CLT is given by the

following equation:

$$\begin{bmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \\ M_x \\ M_y \\ M_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{13} & B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{13} \\ A_{21} & A_{22} & A_{23} & B_{21} & B_{22} & B_{23} \\ A_{31} & A_{32} & A_{33} & B_{31} & B_{32} & B_{33} \\ B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{13} & D_{11} & D_{12} & D_{13} \\ B_{21} & B_{22} & B_{23} & D_{21} & D_{22} & D_{23} \\ B_{31} & B_{32} & B_{33} & D_{31} & D_{32} & D_{33} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \\ \kappa_x \\ \kappa_y \\ \kappa_{xy} \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{or} \quad \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{N} \\ \mathbf{M} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A} & \mathbf{B} \\ \mathbf{B} & \mathbf{D} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \\ \boldsymbol{\kappa} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} and \mathbf{D} are called the extensional, coupling and bending stiffness matrices, respectively. Note that forces and moments are computed per unit length.

The extensional stiffness matrix \mathbf{A} expresses the relationship between normal/shear forces and midplane strains, while the bending stiffness matrix \mathbf{D} expresses the relationship between bending/torsional moments and plate curvatures. The coupling stiffness matrix \mathbf{B} expresses the interaction between extension and bending, which implies that when elements of \mathbf{B} are non-zero, application of normal/shear forces will result in not only midplane strains but also curvatures and plate bending/torsion. It should be noted that in a symmetrical laminate with respect to the midplane, the components of \mathbf{B} will be zero, implying no extension/ bending coupling. The \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} and \mathbf{D} matrices are given by the following equations:

$$A_{ij} = \int_{-\frac{t}{2}}^{\frac{t}{2}} Q_{ij} dz = \sum_{k=1}^n Q_{ij}^{(k)} (z_k - z_{k-1}) \quad (3)$$

$$B_{ij} = \int_{-\frac{t}{2}}^{\frac{t}{2}} Q_{ij} z dz = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^n Q_{ij}^{(k)} (z_k^2 - z_{k-1}^2) \quad (4)$$

$$D_{ij} = \int_{-\frac{t}{2}}^{\frac{t}{2}} Q_{ij} z^2 dz = \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=1}^n Q_{ij}^{(k)} (z_k^3 - z_{k-1}^3) \quad (5)$$

where $Q_{ij}^{(k)}$ is the transformed elasticity matrix of the k lamina, t is the total thickness of the laminate, n is the number of laminae and z_k, z_{k-1} are the distances from the mid-surface of the laminate to the inner/outer surfaces of the k th lamina. In the case that the lamina is aligned with the laminate coordinate system, it holds that $Q_{ij} = C_{ij}$, otherwise transformation of the elasticity matrix C_{ij} is required.

2.2 Numerical Homogenization

According to Hill's energy-based homogenization approach, the work done by the stresses on the strains at the macroscopic level should be equal to the volume averaged work done at the microscopic level. This can be expressed as:

$$\bar{\sigma} : \bar{\varepsilon} = \langle \sigma : \varepsilon \rangle \quad (6)$$

where $\bar{\sigma}$ and $\bar{\varepsilon}$ are the macroscopic stresses and strains. The above equation is satisfied when specific boundary conditions are applied to the volume element, such as uniform strain (Dirichlet), constant traction (Neumann) and periodic BCs [8]. The macroscopic stresses and strains can be computed as volume averaged quantities from the finite elements of a discretized microstructure as follows:

$$\bar{\sigma} = \frac{1}{V} \int_V \sigma dV = \frac{1}{V} \sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_i V_i \quad (7)$$

$$\bar{\varepsilon} = \frac{1}{V} \int_V \varepsilon dV = \frac{1}{V} \sum_{i=1}^n \varepsilon_i V_i \quad (8)$$

where V_i is the element volume, V is the model volume and n is the number of elements.

As ABD matrix homogenization requires force resultants and moments, these quantities are also computed through volume averaging over all elements as follows:

$$\bar{N} = t \frac{1}{V} \sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_i V_i \quad (9)$$

$$\bar{M} = t \frac{1}{V} \sum_{i=1}^n z_i \sigma_i V_i \quad (10)$$

where t is the model thickness, σ_i is the stress computed at the element centroid and z_i is the distance of the element centroid to the midplane.

Homogenization is performed by applying a unit macroscopic strain or curvature at the microstructural model and by setting the remaining strains and curvatures to zero (See. Eq. 2). For each unit state, 6 components of the ABD matrix (one column) can be computed, requiring 6 different unit states, corresponding to each component of the strain/curvature vector, in order to compute the 6×6 ABD matrix. The boundary conditions applied in this work are uniform strain/curvature (Dirichlet) BCs, which can lead to an upper bound of the composite stiffness [9]. Note that models consisting of solid elements are used, therefore BCs are applied entirely through translational degrees of freedom [5].

2.3 Random field computation

In composites that exhibit random inclusion dispersion, spatial variation of the mechanical properties is observed, which can be simulated with random fields. For their computation, images of the composite microstructure are required, usually obtained via CT or SEM imaging techniques. If real composite images are unavailable, computer simulated images can be employed.

The random field computation procedure can be outlined as follows: An image of the composite is first processed with a moving window of dimensions $L_w \times L_w$, which extracts geometrical information and creates FE models (SVEs)

based on local composite morphology, as shown in Fig. 1. In the 2D case, the window moves across the x and y - directions at a step of DL_w . For each FE model, homogenization is performed, thus the apparent mechanical properties are computed at each position of the moving window. As a result, random fields of mechanical properties can be determined from a single composite image, corresponding to one realization. From this realization suitable random field models can be selected and response variability analysis can be performed [14]. This work, however, is limited to determination of random field realizations from images.

Fig. 1: Computer simulated image of the microstructure of a composite material. Illustration of moving window technique and extracted SVE.

Numerical homogenization is performed herein and random fields of the ABD stiffness matrix components are computed. Since different window sizes can lead to different spatial variability, the scale factor $\delta = L_w/d$ is used to characterize computed random fields at different scales, where d is the inclusion diameter in a fiber reinforced composite.

In composites with uniform-like inclusion placement, the resulting random fields can be assumed to be statistically homogeneous. Therefore, the normalized correlation function between ABD stiffness components A and B at a spatial lag (ξ_x^r, ξ_y^s) can be computed through the following equation:

$$\rho(\xi_x^r, \xi_y^s) = \frac{1}{n_x n_y} \sum_{p=1}^{n_x - |r|} \sum_{q=1}^{n_y - |s|} \left(\frac{A(x_p, y_q) - \bar{A}}{\sigma_A} \right) \left(\frac{B(x_p + |\xi_x^r|, y_q + |\xi_y^s|) - \bar{B}}{\sigma_B} \right) \quad (11)$$

where σ_A, σ_B are the standard deviations, \bar{A}, \bar{B} are the spatial average (mean) values of stiffness components A, B and n_x, n_y are the number of windows in

the x and y - directions. For the lag indices, it holds that: $-n_x < r < n_x$ and $-n_y < s < n_y$. For $A = B$, the autocorrelation function can be computed from Eq.11, otherwise cross-correlations are obtained.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Bending stiffness of UD composite

The proposed approach was first tested on various composite representative volume elements (RVEs) and compared to the results derived from CLT. The case of the unidirectional (UD) fiber reinforced composite shown in Fig.2 is examined in this work. The following properties and dimensions are considered: $E_m = 1 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu_m = 0.3$ and $E_{incl} = 100 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu_{incl} = 0.3$, $d = 60 \mu\text{m}$, thickness $t = 200 \mu\text{m}$, dimensions in x- and y-direction $L_x \times L_y = 1000 \mu\text{m} \times 1000 \mu\text{m}$. FE simulations were performed with the ANSA and META pre- and postprocessors using the Abaqus solver.

Fig. 2: A random UD fiber reinforced composite.

The ABD matrix of this composite was computed using three different methods: First, through direct application of the CLT equations (Eq.3-5), which require prior homogenization via extension/shear BCs so that the homogeneous orthotropic material constants can be obtained. Second, it is computed via the proposed bending BC homogenization methodology, after having already been homogenized into an orthotropic material. This was done in order to confirm that the stiffness computed through the proposed methodology is identical to the CLT-derived stiffness for the case of a homogeneous material. Lastly, the proposed homogenization methodology is applied directly to the heterogeneous UD composite, which shows the influence of its geometry on the equivalent bending stiffness.

The computed ABD stiffness matrix components using the three aforementioned methods are shown in Table 1. It is observed that the CLT-derived stiffness and the stiffness computed by bending BC homogenization are almost identical, which shows that the proposed method works as expected for a homogeneous material. On the other hand, bending BCs applied to the heterogeneous composite show some differences compared to the homogeneous orthotropic material. Homogenization via bending BCs allows one to see the effect of the fiber

positions on the effective bending stiffness, whereas this information is lost if the composite is first homogenized via classical BCs and then CLT equations are applied.

The full ABD matrix for the given UD composite can be seen in Table 2.

ABD Matrix Component ($GPa \mu m^3$)	CLT, homogeneous	Bending BCs, homogeneous	Bending BCs, heterogeneous
D_{11}	2.29E7	2.29E7	1.39E7
D_{12}	4.68E5	4.75E5	4.21E5
D_{22}	1.56E6	1.57E6	1.16E6
D_{33}	6.25E5	6.25E5	9.34E5

Table 1: Comparison of bending/torsional ABD components for the composite of Fig.2. Homogeneous refers to the already homogenized composite via classical BCs, whereas heterogeneous refers to the actual composite.

6.83E+03	1.33E+02	6.86E-02	-5.22E+04	-9.10E+02	-1.61E+00
1.33E+02	4.43E+02	-5.33E-02	-9.10E+02	-2.96E+03	1.08E+00
6.86E-02	-5.33E-02	1.76E+02	-1.61E+00	1.08E+00	-1.42E+03
-5.22E+04	-9.10E+02	-1.61E+00	1.39E+07	4.21E+05	-4.12E+02
-9.10E+02	-2.96E+03	1.08E+00	4.21E+05	1.16E+06	2.02E+02
-1.61E+00	1.08E+00	-1.42E+03	-4.12E+02	2.02E+02	9.34E+05

Table 2: Full ABD matrix of composite depicted in Fig.2. In this work, components of the A, B and D matrices are computed in $GPa \mu m$, $GPa \mu m^2$ and $GPa \mu m^3$, respectively.

Neutral plane As the composite is not perfectly symmetric with respect to the midplane, coupling terms are present in the ABD matrix. This happens because the neutral plane of the composite does not coincide with the midplane but lies at a different position, which can lead to inaccurate diagonal stiffness terms [4]. The average position of the true neutral plane can be determined from the two tension and shear unit states, and it is defined as the distance from the midplane, for which moment resultants are equal to zero. From these three unit deformation states, the following three distances are computed:

$$e_x = M_x/F_x, \quad e_y = M_y/F_y, \quad e_{xy} = M_{xy}/F_{xy} \quad (12)$$

which, for heterogeneous composites, do not necessarily coincide. Application of bending and torsional BCs, taking these distances into account, will also lead to zero axial/shear forces, thus applying pure bending/torsion.

For the given UD composite, the following distances from the midplane are computed : $e_x = 7.63 \mu m$, $e_y = 6.77 \mu m$, $e_{xy} = 8.01 \mu m$. Positive distances mean that the neutral plane lies above the midplane of the composite. By taking the true position of the neutral axis into account, the ABD matrix of Table

6.83E+03	1.33E+02	6.86E-02	5.56E+01	7.21E+01	-1.14E+00
1.33E+02	4.43E+02	-5.33E-02	7.21E+01	6.84E+01	6.77E-01
6.86E-02	-5.33E-02	1.76E+02	-1.14E+00	6.77E-01	-1.70E+00
5.56E+01	7.21E+01	-1.14E+00	1.35E+07	4.15E+05	-4.66E+02
7.21E+01	6.84E+01	6.77E-01	4.15E+05	1.14E+06	2.07E+02
-1.14E+00	6.77E-01	-1.70E+00	-4.66E+02	2.07E+02	9.23E+05

Table 3: Full ABD matrix of composite depicted in Fig.2 when taking shifted neutral plane into account.

3 is computed from the given UD composite. In this case, diagonal terms of the D-matrix are only slightly reduced because of the small neutral plane shift. Therefore, effective stiffness is expected to be significantly affected by the neutral plane shift only for large deviations from symmetry with respect to the midplane.

3.2 Random fields in short fiber composite

In this work, real CT image data of a short fiber reinforced composite was employed, in order to compute random fields of the ABD stiffness matrix. The CT data was acquired through the TOMCAT beamline at the Swiss Light Source. It was processed with the RETOMO software of BETA CAE industries, which resulted in a meshed FE model. This model was processed with the moving window technique, as SVE submodels were selected and homogenized with the proposed method, thus obtaining random fields of the ABD matrix components.

An epoxy-glass fiber composite is considered, with the following properties: $E_m = 3 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu_m = 0.395$ and $E_{incl} = 73 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu_{incl} = 0.18$. A 2D slice of the CT model was investigated, with dimensions $L_x \times L_y \times L_z = 1063.4 \mu\text{m} \times 793 \mu\text{m} \times 13 \mu\text{m}$. Random fields for two different scale factors were computed: $\delta = 10$ and $\delta = 20$, which correspond to window sizes $L_w = 52 \mu\text{m}$ and $L_w = 104 \mu\text{m}$, considering an average fiber diameter $d = 5.2 \mu\text{m}$. This required homogenization of 1131 and 266 SVEs, respectively, assuming a window step $DL_w = L_w/2$. The top view of the investigated slice of the material can be seen in Fig.3a. Sample SVEs for the two different scale factors can be seen in Figs.3b,3c.

The computed random fields for both extension/shear and bending/torsion components of the ABD matrix of this composite are depicted in Fig.4 for scale factor $\delta = 10$ and in Fig.5 for scale factor $\delta = 20$. Plots of the autocorrelation function can be seen in Fig.6 for component D_{11} .

With regard to the differences between the two scale factors, it is observed that, variability decreases at higher scales, as the COV appears to decrease. Additionally, correlation lengths appear to increase at larger scale factors, which can be observed in the autocorrelation function plots.

One interesting observation is that despite the relatively low stiffness ratio ($E_{incl}/E_m = 24$), the computed random fields of all stiffness components exhibit a high COV, with a maximum of 24.6% at scale factor $\delta = 10$ and 15.2% for $\delta = 20$. This is expected to lead to significant response variability for structures

Fig. 3: Slice of short fiber composite, top view (a), Sample SVEs at different scale factors (b),(c).

Fig. 4: Random fields of ABD matrix components for scale factor $\delta = 10$.

Fig. 5: Random fields of ABD matrix components for scale factor $\delta = 20$.

Fig. 6: Autocorrelation function of stiffness component D_{11} .

simulated with this material and can be attributed to the large variability of inclusion shapes and orientations in the obtained SVEs.

Additionally, upon close inspection, it becomes apparent that random fields which are computed from the same type of stresses are also highly correlated with each other. For instance, the random fields of ABD matrix components A_{11} and D_{11} are computed from stress component σ_{xx} , and their plots indicate they are correlated. This is confirmed after calculating the cross-correlation coefficients between all components (Table 4), where in this particular case $\rho_{A_{11}}^{D_{11}} = 0.93$. All components appear to be correlated, with the highest correlation being observed

at components computed from the same stresses/in the same direction. This suggests that accurate simulation of these random fields for a response variability analysis requires multivariate (cross-correlated) random field models.

$\delta = 10$									$\delta = 20$								
ρ	A_{11}	A_{12}	A_{22}	A_{33}	D_{11}	D_{12}	D_{22}	D_{33}	ρ	A_{11}	A_{12}	A_{22}	A_{33}	D_{11}	D_{12}	D_{22}	D_{33}
A_{11}	1.00								A_{11}	1.00							
A_{12}	0.71	1.00							A_{12}	0.68	1.00						
A_{22}	0.40	0.62	1.00						A_{22}	0.28	0.65	1.00					
A_{33}	0.76	0.92	0.73	1.00					A_{33}	0.73	0.93	0.73	1.00				
D_{11}	0.93	0.67	0.34	0.71	1.00				D_{11}	0.93	0.64	0.20	0.67	1.00			
D_{12}	0.70	0.84	0.58	0.86	0.75	1.00			D_{12}	0.69	0.84	0.60	0.91	0.70	1.00		
D_{22}	0.35	0.60	0.92	0.69	0.34	0.63	1.00		D_{22}	0.15	0.57	0.95	0.65	0.11	0.57	1.00	
D_{33}	0.72	0.84	0.72	0.85	0.76	0.85	0.76	1.00	D_{33}	0.64	0.87	0.76	0.89	0.65	0.85	0.73	1.00

Table 4: Cross-correlation coefficients of ABD matrix components for short fiber composite.

4 Conclusions

In this work, the spatial variation of the effective bending stiffness in random composites is investigated. For the definition of bending stiffness, the ABD matrix as described by CLT is employed. A method for computing the homogenized ABD matrix of composite shells is implemented, which involves application of classical tension/shear, as well as bending and torsional BCs. It is first applied to a random UD composite, showing the effect of fiber placement on the effective bending stiffness, which cannot be accounted for by merely applying the CLT equations.

The proposed homogenization method is then applied, along with the moving window technique, to CT images of a short fiber composite. By homogenizing SVEs extracted from this composite, random fields of the ABD matrix components are obtained. While variability differs, depending on the size of the SVE, the COV of computed random fields is remarkably high, despite the small material contrast ratios. This can be attributed to the random inclusion shapes and orientations observed in this composite. Additionally, it is observed that the obtained random fields are highly correlated, which would require simulation using multivariate random fields. The computed random ABD matrices can be further employed in a response variability analysis of composite shell structures.

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